

INVESTIGATION OF VIBRATIONS OF REINFORCED CONCRETE RIBBED SHELLS

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Abstract. *The study of vibrational movements and transients in deformable shells is of great practical importance. Structures in the form of plates and shells interacting with the elastic medium are widely used in engineering and construction. The article studies the stress-strain state (SSS) of flat reinforced concrete ribbed shells under the action of short-term and long-term loads. It is assumed that the rheological properties of reinforced concrete obey the linear theory of hereditary creep. The analysis of the results of testing the strength and stability of shells, supported by ribs, and their comparison with similar results of the calculation of smooth shells, both for linear-elastic deformation and creep problems. It is shown that the study of reinforced concrete shells cannot take into account factors such as geometric nonlinearity and transverse shifts.*

Keywords: *flat reinforced concrete shells, ribs, creep, strength, stability, permissible load.*

Introduction. The study of oscillatory processes is of great importance for modern engineering. Its development is related to the increase in speeds, pressures, temperatures, the continuous growth of power and high-speed capabilities of machines and mechanisms, as well as the increase in aerodynamic effects of the flow of the medium. At the same time, there is a trend toward better utilization of the load-bearing capacity of structures and reducing their weight. This leads to increased dynamic loads on the elements of machines and structures [1].

The development of modern technology increasingly relies on the achievements of fundamental and applied scientific research. Engineering structures and constructions are becoming more complex, making it difficult to design them without preliminary detailed analysis of the behavior of these structures or their elements under certain conditions [2].

Significant resources are spent worldwide on the research of various types of oscillations. The main goal of these studies is to determine the role of oscillatory processes for the designed object. When oscillations are desirable, research is conducted to regulate them. When they are undesirable, the task is to identify the causes of the oscillations and prevent them. One of the important technical issues is determining the period and frequency of natural oscillations of structures [3].

1. Statement of the problem. As is known, the mathematical model for the deformation of any shell consists of geometric and physical relations, as well as equilibrium equations or the functional of the total energy of shell deformations. Solving such systems of equations represents a complex mathematical problem. The mathematical models and algorithms for the analysis of shallow shells (including ribbed and reinforced concrete ones) are presented in detail in works [4].

In the study of reinforced concrete shells, a significant difficulty is the assignment of stiffness and deformation characteristics of the shell. Reinforced concrete is a composite material, the behavior of which, like that of ordinary concrete, can be described under certain conditions by

formulas for an elastic-creeping homogeneous medium. It is assumed that the rheological properties of reinforced concrete obey the linear theory of hereditary creep [5]. The deformation characteristics of reinforced concrete shells are introduced by the modulus of elasticity of concrete E_b and two measures of the creep of reinforced concrete C_N , C_M . According to the formulas of the linear mechanics of a symmetrically reinforced elastic-creeping material (reinforced concrete), the calculation formulas take the form [6].

$$\varepsilon_0(t) = \frac{N}{A} \left[\frac{1}{E_b} + C_N(t, \tau) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\omega(t) = \frac{M}{I} \left[\frac{1}{E_b} + C_M(t, \tau) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$C_N(t, \tau) = C(t, \tau) + \int_{\tau}^t R_N(t, \theta) \left[\frac{1}{E_b} + C(\theta, \tau) \right] d\theta \quad (3)$$

$$C_M(t, \tau) = C(t, \tau) + \int_{\tau}^t R_M(t, \theta) \left[\frac{1}{E_b} + C(\theta, \tau) \right] d\theta \quad (4)$$

where $R_N(t, \tau)$ - resolvent of the kernel; $\frac{A_{s,red}}{A} E_b \frac{\partial C(t, \theta)}{\partial \theta}$; $R_M(t, \tau)$ resolvent of the kernel;

$\frac{I_{s,red}}{I} E_b \frac{\partial C(t, \theta)}{\partial \theta}$; N, M - internal forces in the cross-sections of the structure; E_b - modulus of elasticity of concrete; $A_{s, red}$, $I_{s, red}$ - reduced cross-sectional area and moment of inertia of reinforcement; C_N, C_M - deformation characteristics of reinforced concrete (two measures of the creep of reinforced concrete); θ - time corresponding to the age of the concrete[7].

2. Analysis of calculation results of shallow shells. Using the developed software package "PologObolochka" calculations of shallow reinforced concrete shells with hinge-fixed supports along the contour and subjected to uniformly distributed loads were performed. The main parameters of the considered shells are: $a = b = 54 \text{ m}$; $R_1 = R_2 = 135,9 \text{ m}$; $h = 0,09 \text{ m}$; The shells are made of class B40 concrete. Smooth (without ribs) shells and shells reinforced with 18 regularly arranged stiffening ribs of height $3h$ and width $2h$, oriented parallel to the coordinate axes, are studied.

Figure 1 shows the «load \bar{P} - deflection \bar{W} » dependencies for a smooth shell under linear-elastic deformation. All solutions are performed in dimensionless parameters. The values of \bar{P} , \bar{W} , $\bar{\sigma}$ are determined by the formulas:

$$\bar{P} = \frac{a^4 q}{Eh^4}; \quad \bar{W} = \frac{W}{h}; \quad \bar{\sigma} = \frac{a^2 \sigma}{h^2 E}. \quad (5)$$

In assessing the strength of the concrete shells, the Coulomb-Mohr criterion is used. Below, as an illustration of the calculation results, functions of the stress distribution are presented.

$\bar{\sigma}_g = \bar{\sigma}_1 - \frac{\bar{R}_b}{R_b} \bar{\sigma}_3$ over the shell field under different loads \bar{P} . Here $\bar{\sigma}_1 < \bar{\sigma}_2 < \bar{\sigma}_3$ - are the principal stresses, which are determined by solving equation (6)

$$\bar{\sigma}^3 - (\bar{\sigma}_x + \bar{\sigma}_y) \bar{\sigma}^2 + (\bar{\sigma}_x \bar{\sigma}_y - \bar{\tau}_{xy}^2 - \bar{\tau}_{xz}^2 - \bar{\tau}_{yz}^2) \bar{\sigma} - (2\bar{\tau}_{yz} \bar{\tau}_{xz} \bar{\tau}_{xy} - \bar{\tau}_x \bar{\tau}_{yz}^2 - \bar{\tau}_y \bar{\tau}_{xz}^2 - \bar{\tau}_z \bar{\tau}_{xy}^2) = 0 \quad (6)$$

The dimensionless stresses $\bar{\sigma}_x$, $\bar{\sigma}_y$, $\bar{\tau}_{xy}$, $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$, $\bar{\tau}_{yz}$ are determined on the upper surface of the shells.

The smooth shell under linear-elastic deformation loses stability at a load equal to $\bar{P}_{ct} = 70100$ ($q_{ct} = 19,47 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa}$). The allowable load on the shell is $-\bar{P}_{add} = 13920$ ($q_{add} = 3,87 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa}$).

Fig 1. The «load \bar{P} - deflection \bar{W} » dependencies for a smooth shell

Figure 2 shows the «load \bar{P} - deflection \bar{W} » dependence for a similar shell, reinforced with 18 ribs, under linear-elastic deformation.

Figure 2. The « \bar{P} - \bar{W} » dependence for a shell reinforced with 18 ribs.

Figure 3. Stress fields $\bar{\sigma}_g$ for smooth (3,a) and ribbed (3,b) shells

Fig. 3,a. Stresses $\bar{\sigma}_g$ at $\bar{P} = 35000$

Fig. 3,b. Stresses $\bar{\sigma}_g$ at $\bar{P} = 35000$

In Figure 3, the following designations are used: $\xi = \frac{x}{a}$, $\eta = \frac{y}{b}$,

The shell reinforced with ribs under linear-elastic deformation loses stability at $\bar{P}_{ct} = 160500$ ($q_{ct} = 44,58 \times 10^{-3}$ MPa). The allowable load on them (based on strength conditions) $\bar{P}_{add} = 25000$ ($q_{add} = 6,94 \times 10^{-3}$ MPa). The calculations of the shells were also performed taking into account the development of creep deformations.

The table below provides a small sample of critical times t_{ct} , corresponding to the loss of stability of shells due to creep (to illustrate the dynamics of changes in t_{ct} depending on the change in the magnitude of the acting loads). In the first numerical column of the table are the values of allowable loads on the shells and the corresponding critical times t_{ct} .

Table 1

Critical time t_{ct} corresponding to the loss of shell stability due to creep

Shell type	Critical time t_{ct} under acting loads, days			
Smooth shell	\bar{P}	13920	20000	40000
	t_{ct}	335	250	55
Ribbed shell	\bar{P}	25000	50000	120000
	t_{ct}	280	12S	20

Conclusion. The investigation of the stability of smooth and ribbed reinforced concrete shells under short-term loads showed that the allowable loads (based on ensuring the strength of the concrete) constitute 16-20% of the critical loads. The critical time at which shells lose stability due to creep decreases as the acting long-term loads increase. The critical loads corresponding to this time do not exceed the allowable loads for shells operating under conditions of linear-elastic deformation. Under long-term loads, due to the development of creep deformations, an increase and redistribution of stresses across the shell field is observed. The highest stresses occur in the corner zones of the shells (see Fig 3). It was shown that in the study of shallow reinforced concrete ribbed shells, factors such as geometric nonlinearity and transverse shears can be disregarded.

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